

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF LEADERSHIP ACTIVITY

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Abstract: leadership psychological literacy any individual characteristic, situation, circumstance, conflict, personality resistance, attitude a wide possibility of applying in practice a rational and factor –individual or differential approach to problem solving complex conditions create the basis for the emergence of a personal style. Consequently, the manager should be guided not only by psychological knowledge about the individual typological characteristics of employees, but also by information about socio-psychological conditions, patterns, the development of phenomena, factors causing them, moving mechanisms for solving social problems with firm acceptance of them in the process and stages of its implementation. Otherwise, in a team that stabilizes the psychological environment when managing such microstructures as a group, with the correct organization of interpersonal relationships, when establishing the production of interaction between people, affectation, impressions of mutual understanding of such complex experiences as empathy, defects and shortcomings in understanding the duration of power are allowed.

Keywords: management, modernization, management psychology, labor, motivation, labor activity.

СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ ЛИДЕРСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Аннотация: лидерская психологическая грамотность любая отдельная характеристика, ситуация, обстоятельство, конфликт, сопротивление личности, отношение широкая возможность применения на практике рационального и факторно – индивидуального или дифференциального подхода к решению проблем комплексные условия создают основу для возникновения личностного стиля. Следовательно, руководитель должен руководствоваться не только психологическими знаниями об индивидуально-типологических особенностях работников, но и информацией о социально-психологических состояниях, закономерностях, развитии явлений, факторах, вызывающих их, движущихся механизмах решения социальных проблем с твердым принятием их в процессе и этапах его выполнения. В противном случае в коллективе, стабилизирующем психологическую среду при управлении такими микроструктурами, как группа, при правильной организации межличностных отношений, при налаживании производства взаимодействия между людьми, аффектации, впечатления взаимопонимания таких сложных переживаний, как эмпатия, допускаются дефекты и недочеты в понимании длительности силы.

Ключевые слова: управление, модернизация, психология управления, труд, мотивация, трудовая деятельность.

RAHBARLIK FAOLIYATINING IJTIMOYIY-PSIXOLOGIK OMILLARI

Annotatsiya: Rahbarlik psixologik savodxonlik har qaysi alohida xususiyat, vaziyat, holat, ziddiyat, shaxs qarshiligi, munosabat muammo yechimiga oqilona va omilkorlik bilan individual yoki differentsial yondashishni amaliyotga tatbiq etishga keng ko'lamli imkoniyat puxta shart – sharoit shaxsiy uslub vujudga kelishiga negiz yaratadi. Binobarin rahbar xodimlarning individual tipologik xususiyatlari bo'yicha psixologik bilimlar bilan qanoat hosil qilmasdan, balki ijtimoiy psixologik holatlar, qonuniyatlar, hodisalar rivoji, ularni keltirib chiqaruvchi omillar

harakatlanuvchi mexanizmlar ijtimoiy muammolarning yechimi jarayonda qat'iy qabul qilish va uni bajarilishi bosqichlari to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar bilan qo'llanilishi lozim. Aks holda jamoa guruh singari mikrotuzilmalarni boshqarishda psixologik muhitni barqarorlashtirida shaxslararo munosabatlarni to'g'ri tashkil qilishda ishlab chiqarishni yo'lga qo'yishda odamlar o'rtasida o'zaro ta'sir, ta'sirlanish, taassurot o'zaro tushunish hamdardlik kabi murakkab kechinmalarkuchi davomiyligini anglab yetishda nuqson va kamchiliklarga yo'l qo'yiladi.

Keywords: boshqaruv, modernizatsiya, boshqaruv psixologiyasi, mehnat, rag'bat, mehnat faoliyati.

INTRODUCTION:

- Persons preparing for the position of leader should first familiarize themselves with the requirements for them and firmly decide on the weaknesses of self-perfection. It is necessary to firmly decide on the weaknesses of these considerations. The requirements dictated by the position on the psyche of the leader cover the fronts, which relate to three different categories: cognitive, emotional-emotional volitional qualities. The requirements related to cognition and the process of cognition are as follows:

- Degree of mastery of attention characteristics;
- Achieving a high level of intuition and perception;
- Images of mysticism, the reading ability to notice time;
- Images of imagination and a penchant for creative imagination;
- Logic, speed and meaningfulness of memory strength, stability thoroughness and breadth of scope;
- The content of speech, speech activity and speech skills;
- Speech, speech activity and indicator of speech activity;
- Non-standard of efficiency, scalability, creativity, resourcefulness of thinking, conservation activities.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Socio-psychological methods of management are a means of managing the producer and certain individuals with an impact on their social extremes and psychological characteristics. The application of socio-psychological methods of Management an in-depth study of the social phenomena occurring at the enterprise requires knowledge of the psychological (mental) factors that affect the mood of the nervous system of employees. In the conditions of production, sociology studies labor factors that are the basis of the formation of social communication of people, studies social systems, including the patterns of development and functioning of the production system, the patterns of behavior of people in different strata of society.

Social psychology studies the features of Group and public psychology, their influence on the consciousness and behavior of the individual, factors that stimulate the activities of people, mood, factors that form social thought. Personality psychology studies the types of higher nervous activity and human temperament, character, personality Will, ability, emotion, memory, ability to understand and feel, Labor psychology studies the activities of labor activities, including managers and specialists (professional characteristics and abilities, methods of training personnel, mode of work and rest, methods of selection and evaluation of personnel, psychological aspects of the labor process).

Spiritually person there should be spiritual cleansing, awakening of the soul. We can say that it is a manifestation of goodness if a person and our current youth are able to embody these

qualities, enrich their inner world and develop the will to approach him as a human being, faith in general and a sense of endurance. When indifference and indifference prevail in the spiritual education of our youth, when the most pressing issues are left to egoism, spirituality becomes the weakest and most vulnerable point. Or, conversely, where vigilance and zeal, high intelligence and contemplation prevail, spirituality becomes a powerful force.

A person who has adopted Eastern morality and universal human ideas is a person of high spirituality, that is, a spiritually mature, perfect person. Spiritual perfection is characterized by a direct connection with a person's worldview, his beliefs, psyche, norms of behavior, morality. Spiritually mature people think about the fate and well-being of the people, about the fate of the Motherland and its development. They don't want to live in dumbness, depending.

Spiritual maturity of young people is a very broad concept, on the basis of which it is important to educate a healthy generation with a healthy worldview. After all, the main goal of education is to lead a conscious life in society, to create a highly cultured, intellectual and prosperous environment.

The importance of socio-psychological methods also increases as people change their way of thinking and they increase their cultural and cognitive levels. In such conditions, the needs and interests of the individual change towards the spiritual sphere. An important factor in satisfaction with one's own labor is the favorable socio-psychological situation in production, in which manufacturers interact well with the leader. Socio-psychological methods of management are based on the application of the existing social mechanism (system of interaction, social needs) in production.

Social methods of management are carried out by means of social regulation. Methods of social regulation are used in order to regulate and harmonize social relations by identifying and adjusting the goals and interests of various groups and individuals. Their sentence includes the regulations of social organizations, contracts, mutual obligations, the system of selection, distribution of workers and satisfaction of social needs. Methods of social regulation are also used in order to increase the activity of the human factor, to democratize management. Psychological methods of management are aimed at regulating the relationship between people through the organization of an optimal psychological state in the team.

Psychological methods include the organization of small groups and communities, the humanization of Labor, the selection of qualified values and their identification, etc. The application of the method of organizing small groups and teams allows you to determine the optimal quantitative-qualitative ratio between workers in a small group. Humanization of labor activity is understood as the use of the influence of Colors, music, the elimination of the same, unchanging Labor, the expansion of the creative approach. The essence of professional selection is to choose in such a way that the zinc properties of people are most suitable for their executors. The mental characteristics of a person include his interests and inclinations, abilities, temperament and character. Therefore, when a leader guides a person, he must set himself the task of studying the formation and development of human mental properties, knowing his interest and ability, temperament and temperament. The mental properties of a person cannot be distinguished in human activity, since the properties of the ability and temperament of a person are manifested in his activity and behavior.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Human life and mass activity shape his state of mind. It is impossible to realize how a person lives, arises not knowing what he is dealing with, the ability to this or that thing is developed, the

verb is formed. A person first of all assesses himself as a creative person. The worker does not immediately come to look at Labor from such a point of view: material needs are primary, and after they get used to them, relatively high human needs are put forward. Human activity is based on certain motivating factors and is aimed at achieving a certain goal. The motivating factor is the goal attitude is the core of human activity. In a general sense, the motivating factor is the motivating factor for the functioning of a person, and the goal is what a person wants to achieve as a result of its implementation. The motivating factor is the inner strength of a person's behavior.

If the factor that stimulates human activity and the goal set for itself is aimed at the near future, it is called short-term, if they cover the short-term. With the level of the motivating factor, the attitude of a person towards work, achievement and failure is inextricably linked. Only a short-term motivating factor is a source of creative attitude to work. An important feature inherent in a leader is a good knowledge of the factors that stimulate the activities of people, the ability to interest everyone to perform one or another task. This is especially true when working with young people who need to get a job at one enterprise or another and find out what awaits them in the future.

CONCLUSION

The work of a leader can be compared to the knowledge of the work of a conductor who has learned which violin to play, which instrument to play music, who can play Wrong, who needs to know which ground to put. One lack of satisfaction of mental characteristics with the requirements of the work he performs leads to the fact that dissatisfaction with his profession leads to an attempt to change it, an increase in the likelihood of making a mistake, and, as a result, a decrease in labor productivity.. on the contrary, if a person is busy with work that is able to fully show his abilities, he will be satisfied with his work, will quickly master the profession, and labor productivity will be higher. It is wrong to consider that only material incentive is important for a person. It is also important for him to hiss that he has his own personality in a great common cause, to manifest himself through work, to be proud of his qualifications, to be respected by his comrades, etc.

Many people argue that personal well-being should be achieved not through personal success achieved at the expense of others, but at the expense of the labor that they have contributed to the country's economy. Research has shown that the ragging factors affecting the attitude of Labor to labor are distributed in the following order: labor leprosy, work time, the possibility of obtaining a high position, the fun of work, the organization of Labor, the attitude of the administration towards the worker.

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